

NEURODERMATITIS CIRCUMSCRIPTA: CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Introduction: Neurodermatitis circumscripta is estimated to occur in approximately 10% of the population. The highest prevalence usually occurs in middle to late adulthood and often peaks at 30 to 50 years of age, most likely due to the significant increase in stress at this stage of life. The condition is more common in women than men with a ratio of 2:1. Case Description: A 43-year-old patient complaints of redness and itching in the wound in the upper ankle area of the right foot that has worsened in the last 1 week. The patient reported a previous episode of similar symptoms, which occurred in a different location, specifically around the border of the right toe and spread circularly accompanied by redness and blackness. Itching worse when the patient sweats. Dermatologic status was found on the dextra inferior extremity, erythema plaques appeared and some parts had hyperpigmentation accompanied by squamous, exoriation and plaque-size lichenification, irregular shape with firm boundaries scattered only unilaterally on the dextra extremity. This patient was treated with desoximethasone cream 0.25%, gentamycin cream 0.1% and cetirizine 10mg. Conclusion: Neurodermatitis circumscripta or lichen simplex chronicus is a chronic inflammatory skin disease. Topical therapies that can be given to patients are potent topical steroids, antibiotics and keratolytic agents. Lichen simplex chronicus usually improves with treatment, but some case can become persistent, especially when in the genital area.

Keyword: Neurodermatitis, Lichen Simplex, Lichenification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Neurodermatitis circumscripta, also known as lichen simplex chronicus is a form of localized pruritus that is long-lasting and accompanied by secondary dermatitis. It is one of the most common types of chronic itchy conditions, estimated to affect more than 10% of the population. Despite its high prevalence, research into the causes and pathogenesis of lichen simplex chronicus is limited, making it a difficult condition to treat. However, in recent years, neurodermatitis circumscripta has been suggested to be influenced by stress, resulting in an itch-scratch cycle. Emotional stress leading to irritation and the urge to scratch the skin is often cyclical, with the resulting plaques causing more stress and chronic itch, pigmentation changes in the affected skin, and the potential for spreading to larger areas. (1,2)

Neurodermatitis circumscripta, also known as lichen simplex chronicus, is a chronic, itchy, localized inflammatory skin condition, usually on the ankles or extremities, characterized by lichenification phenomena in the form of thick, scaly patches. Lichenification occurs as a response of the skin to repeated scratching and rubbing over a long period of time. Thickened, potentially discolored plaques and lesions may form as a result of repeated scratching of the affected area. (2)

Lichen simplex chronicus is estimated to occur in approximately 12% of the population. The highest prevalence usually occurs in middle to late adulthood and often peaks at ages 30 to 50 years, likely due to significant increases in stress at this stage in a person's life. The disorder is more common in women than in men by a ratio of 2:1. (2)

The purpose of this case report is to present the clinical picture, diagnosis, and therapy of neurodermatitis circumscripta found in the dermatology and venereology polyclinic of Woodward Hospital in a 43-year-old man.

2. CASE REPORT

The patient was 43 years old with complaints of redness and itching of the wound in the upper ankle area of the right foot which had worsened in the last 1 week. There was a previous history of the same complaint but in a different predilection area, namely around the upper edge of the right toe area and spread circularly accompanied by redness and blackness. Itching worsens when the patient sweats, there is a history of previous treatment, namely routinely taking cetirizine 1 x 1 and ointment given by the doctor. There was a change, but the area of the wound spread moved and expanded accompanied by thickening of the skin due to frequent scratching and redness. Physical examination found that the patient's general condition was mildly ill, compos mentis consciousness (E4M6V5) with good nutritional status.

A review of the dermatologic examination found on the dextra inferior extremity appeared erythematous plaques and some parts have been hyperpigmented accompanied by squamous, exoriation and lichenification plaque-sized, irregular shape with firm boundaries scattered only unilateral dextra extremity.

Figure 1. In the dextra inferior extremity, erythematous plaques are seen and some parts have hyperpigmentation accompanied by squamous, exoriated and lichenified plaque-sized, irregularly shaped with firm boundaries scattered only unilaterally in the dextra extremity

This patient was given topical therapy in the form of desoximethasone cream 0.25% applied to the lesion area 2 times a day, gentamycin cream 0.1% applied to the lesion area 2 times a day and oral therapy in the form of cetirizine 10mg once a day.

3. DISCUSSION

In this case, the diagnosis was made based on history and findings from history, physical examination and dermatological status. Anamnesis review found that a 43-year-old man came to the Dermatology and Venereology Polyclinic of Woodward Hospital with complaints of redness in the right foot area accompanied by thickening of the skin. The patient had a history of previous treatment with the same complaint but in a different area, namely near the toe area, but the longer the treatment was given, the patient's complaint area had moved around the ankle. Foot part on. Complaint patient started from around 1 month Which Then with itching in the foot area near the toes which was initially the size of a corn kernel, but the patient ignored the complaint because

he thought it was just a normal wound. The patient admitted that he had given betadine to the itchy wound area, but the complaint did not decrease or disappear.

The Development of redness on the foot area and itching that continued to be felt made the disease area more widespread. The patient had been given ointment and drinking medicine which was routinely done until his complaint improved in the previous 2 weeks. However, in the last 1 week the patient again felt the same complaint but in a different area on the right leg. The itching felt by the patient worsened and required him to scratch the wound area. According to his confession, the complaint became lighter when the patient scratched it and causes thickening of the wound area and the wound expands. The complaint was aggravated when the patient sweated.

According to Habib (2021), LSC is often classified as a neurodermatological disorder, due to the prominent pruritus component and the involvement of neuropsychological factors. The book Dermatology by Jean L. Bologna (2017) also mentions that LSC results from repeated mechanical stimulation of the skin that results in the release of inflammatory mediators, which then exacerbates itching and reinforces the scratching cycle.(3,4)

The diagnosis of LSC is generally clinical based on the history and appearance of typical lesions. However, in atypical cases, histopathological examination can be performed which will show epidermal thickening (acanthosis), hyperkeratosis and lymphocytic infiltrates in the upper dermis as signs of chronic inflammation.

Clinically, atopic dermatitis lesions appear as lichenified lesions, which are usually solitary but can be multiple, and range in size from lenticular to plaques. The initial stage consists of erythematous and edematous papules or clusters with scales and blisters and persistent lichenified plaques with hyperpigmentation or hypopigmentation. The center of the lesion is thick, dry, and scaly, while the edges are hyperpigmented. (5,6)

Lichen simplex chronicus can be considered as a secondary manifestation of chronic atopic dermatitis, resulting from repeated scratching of the itchy area. They are closely related in terms of pathophysiology, precipitating factors, and management strategies. Effective management of atopic dermatitis will also contribute to preventing or reducing the incidence of Lichen simplex chronicus.(7)

Based on the findings obtained, this indicates that neurodermatitis circumscripta or chronic simplex dermatitis (CS) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease with common characteristics, namely repeated itching and scratching cycles. This is in accordance with the theory that this is a disease. Atopic dermatitis is divided into distributed skin lesions and local skin lesions, depending on the severity of the skin lesions. Lesions are commonly found on the neck, ankles, lateral legs, scalp, forearm extensors, scrotum, pubic bone, and vulva. Atopic dermatitis is characterized by thickened, dry, scaly skin, and hyperpigmentation or hypopigmentation when scratching or rubbing the itchy skin area. (8,9)

No examination was performed on this patient. Support. If necessary, tests to support the differential diagnosis can also be performed. If the clinical picture is suspicious, histopathological examination can be performed. A complete dermatological examination is performed to exclude pure primary inflammatory skin diseases and to evaluate secondary scratch lesions, such as typical isolated lichenified plaques. A biopsy can help differentiate LSC from other diseases with similar clinical manifestations, such as: hypertrophic lichen planus, psoriasis-like rashes, contact dermatitis, squamous cell carcinoma, mycosis fungoides. (1,6)

Successful treatment depends on identifying and eliminating the triggering factors and ending the itch-scratch cycle. Topical and systemic treatments can help reduce the symptoms of eczema. Low-potency steroid creams may be used, but if lichenification occurs, ointments should be considered. Oral antihistamines are indicated in the evening to control nighttime scratching.(10)

Topical therapy that can be given to patients consists of topical steroids, antibiotics, and keratolytics. Patients with local neurodermatitis should be given strong topical steroids. Corticosteroids have anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, anti-pruritic, and vasoconstrictor effects. Topical steroid therapy that can be given to these patients is 0.25% desoxymethasone cream which is the treatment of choice to reduce inflammation, pruritus, and keratosis. Desoxymethasone is a potent topical steroid that increases protein synthesis, reduces inflammation, and causes vasoconstriction. For maximum efficacy, use topical corticosteroids two to three times a day for up to two weeks.(11)

The patient received systemic therapy, namely cetirizine, an antihistamine. Cetirizine is a second-generation antihistamine that works by blocking H1 receptors in the dermis. Because histamine is a mediator that causes itching in the skin, antihistamines can relieve symptoms of itching in the skin.(12)

Focal neurodermatitis can be diagnosed based on the lesions, areas of predilection, and underlying etiology and is differentiated from lichen planus, psoriasis, and tinea pedis.

3.1. Lichen Planus

Figure 2. *Lichen Planus*

Lichen Planus occurs through immunological mechanisms. Cellular immunity is thought to be involved in the spread of the disease. CD4+ and CD8+ T cells are present in lichen planus lesions. Lichen planus begins as red patches that turn into purple papules after a few weeks. The first lesions most often appear on the extremities, especially the lower extremities. The extremities are usually symmetrical and tend to affect the flexor muscles of the wrists, arms, and legs. It also affects the thighs, hips, trunk, and neck. The disease can also affect the mucous membranes of the mouth and genitals of the thighs, lower back, trunk, and neck. It can also affect the oral and genital mucosa.(12)

3.2. Psoriasis

Figure 3. *Psoriasis*

This disease can affect the skin, nails, mucous membranes, and joints, but not the hair. Until now, there is no comprehensive understanding of the pathogenesis of psoriasis, but the role of autoimmunity and genetics can be the basis for therapeutic principles. Psoriasis can appear in the form of erythematous plaques covered with white scales, which when the scales are removed are accompanied by bloody spots, spread from the tip of the needle to the spots, cover most areas of the body, and are generally symmetrical.(12)

3.3. Tinea Pedis

Figure 4. *Tinea Pedis*

Tinea pedis is a dermatophytosis disease of the feet, especially between the toes and on the soles of the feet. Another form is called moccasin foot. It occurs all over your feet, from the soles of your feet to the tips and tops of your feet. The most common pathogens are *Trichophyton rubrum* and *Trichophyton interdigitalis*. The dominant dermatophytes vary by geographic location (related to climate characteristics and social factors) and can change over time.(12,13)

The skin appears thickened and scaly. Erythema is usually mild and occurs mainly at the edge of the lesion. Papules and sometimes vesicles may also be seen at the edge of the lesion. In the subacute form, blisters, bullous pustules, and sometimes bullae are seen.(12,13) The prognosis of peripheral neurodermatitis improves depending on the treatment the patient receives. It has also been described in the literature stating that the patient's prognosis is good if itching, mild lichenification, and pigmentation changes can be overcome. Relapses can occur if the patient experiences stress or increased emotional stress. The prognosis depends on the patient's condition. The prognosis is worse if the disease is accompanied by mental disorders or other diseases. Atopic dermatitis can be a persistent and recurrent lesion. Exacerbations can be triggered by a response to emotional stress.(11,13)

4. CONCLUSIONS

Neurodermatitis circumscripta or lichen simplex chronicus is a chronic inflammatory skin disease characterised by intense itching that triggers repeated scratching cycles. These cycles lead to skin thickening (lichenification), squamous, excoriation and changes in skin pigmentation. The diagnosis is made clinically based on history and dermatological findings. Management aims to break the itch-scratch cycle and manage inflammation through topical and systemic therapies.

Topical therapies that can be given to patients include potent topical steroids, topical antibiotics and keratolytic agents to reduce inflammation, prevent secondary infections and help exfoliate thickened skin. Oral antihistamines are also needed to control pruritus, especially at night. Lichen simplex chronicus generally improves with treatment, but in some cases it may become persistent, especially when the lesions are in the genital area or when precipitating factors such as emotional stress are not addressed. Therefore, a comprehensive treatment approach, including patient education, trigger avoidance, and long-term care is essential to achieve optimal treatment outcomes and prevent recurrence.

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